

SKALYAR ARGUMENTLI VEKTOR FUNKSIYA VA UNING XOSSALARI

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ABSTRACT

agar $t=t_0$ nuqtada $x(t), y(t), z(t)$ funksiyalar limitga ega bo'lsa, (t) vektor funksiyaning $t=t_0$ nuqtadagi limiti

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow t_0} \vec{r}(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow t_0} x(t)\vec{i} + \lim_{t \rightarrow t_0} y(t)\vec{j} + \lim_{t \rightarrow t_0} z(t)\vec{k}$$

bo'ladi.

Skalyar argumentli vektor funksiya

Ta'rif: Agar E sohadan olingan har bir haqiqiy t songa biror qoidaga ko'ra bittadan $\vec{r}(t)$ vektor mos qo'yilgan bo'lsa, E to'plamda t haqiqiy o'zgaruvchining vektor funksiyasi berilgan deyiladi.

Agar R^3 fazodagi bazis $(\vec{i}, \vec{j}, \vec{k})$ bo'lsa, u holda vektor funksiyaning

$$\vec{r}(t) = x(t)\vec{i} + y(t)\vec{j} + z(t)\vec{k} \quad (1)$$

ko'rinishda yozish mumkin. Bunda $x(t), y(t), z(t)$ lar \vec{r} vektorning koordinata o'qlaridagi proeksiyalari. Vektor funksiyaning berilishi bilan uchta skalyar funksiya $x(t), y(t), z(t)$ larning berilishi teng kuchlidir. Agar $\vec{r}(t)$ vektorning boshlang'ich nuqtasi koordinatalar boshiga joylashtirilsa (bunday vektor radius-vektor deb ataladi), u holda $\vec{r}(t)$ vektor uchlarining geometrik 1-rasm

o'rnini vektor funksiyaning godografi deyiladi.

Godografning fizik ma'nosi shundan iboratki, agar t parametr vaqt deb olinsa, $\vec{r}(t)$ radius-vektorning godografi harakatdagi nuqtaning traektoriyasini bildiradi. (1-rasm)

Vektor funksiyaning hosilasi.

Agar $t=t_0$ nuqtada $x(t), y(t), z(t)$ funksiyalar limitga ega bo'lsa, $\vec{r}(t)$ vektor funksiyaning $t=t_0$ nuqtadagi limiti

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow t_0} \vec{r}(t) = \lim_{t \rightarrow t_0} x(t)\vec{i} + \lim_{t \rightarrow t_0} y(t)\vec{j} + \lim_{t \rightarrow t_0} z(t)\vec{k} \quad (2)$$

bo'ladi.

Agar $\lim_{t \rightarrow t_0} \vec{r}(t) = \vec{r}(t_0)$ bo'lsa, vektor-funksiya $t=t_0$ da uzluksiz deyiladi.

Endi $\vec{r}(t)$ vektor-funksiyaning hosilasi haqidagi masalaga o'tamiz.

$\Delta \vec{r}(t_0)$ vektorning boshi koordinatalar boshida deb faraz qilamiz. Bu holda $\vec{r}(t)$ vektor-funksiyaning godografi parametrik ko'rinishda $x=x(t)$, $y=y(t)$, $z=z(t)$ tengliklar bilan berilgan fazoviy egri chiziqdan iborat bo'ladi. O'zgaruvchi t ning shu egri chiziqdagi M_0 nuqtaga mos keladigan $t=t_0$ qiymatini olib, unga Δt orttirma beramiz. U vaqtda

$$\vec{r}(t_0 + \Delta t) = x(t_0 + \Delta t)\vec{i} + y(t_0 + \Delta t)\vec{j} + z(t_0 + \Delta t)\vec{k}$$

vektorni hosil qilamiz, bu vektor egri chiziqda biror M nuqtani aniqlaydi. (2-rasm).

Vektor-funksiya orttirmasini tuzamiz va uning skalyar argument orttirmasiga nisbatini qaraymiz:

2 - rasm

$$\frac{\Delta \vec{r}}{\Delta t} = \frac{\vec{r}(t_0 + \Delta t) - \vec{r}(t_0)}{\Delta t} = \frac{x(t_0 + \Delta t) - x(t_0)}{\Delta t} \vec{i} + \frac{y(t_0 + \Delta t) - y(t_0)}{\Delta t} \vec{j} + \frac{z(t_0 + \Delta t) - z(t_0)}{\Delta t} \vec{k} \quad (3)$$

Ta'rif. Agar $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ da $\frac{\Delta \vec{r}}{\Delta t}$ nisbatning chekli limiti mavjud bo'lsa, u limit $\vec{r}(t)$ vektor-

funksiyaning $t=t_0$ nuqtadagi hosilasi deyiladi va $\vec{r}'(t_0)$ yoki $\frac{d\vec{r}(t_0)}{dt}$ orqali belgilanadi.

$$\vec{r}'(t_0) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta \vec{r}}{\Delta t} \quad (4)$$

Hosila vektorning yo'nalishini aniqlash maqsadida chizmaga e'tibor bersak, $t \rightarrow t_0$ da M nuqta M_0 ga, M_0M kesuvchi esa urinmaga intiladi. Demak, hosila vektor $\vec{r}'(t_0)$ parametrning o'sish tomoniga urinma bo'ylab yo'nalgan vektor bo'ladi.

Ravshanki, (10.3) tenglikdan $\vec{r}'(t_0) = x'(t_0)\vec{i} + y'(t_0)\vec{j} + z'(t_0)\vec{k}$ ekanligi, bundan esa hosilani hisoblashning asosiy qoidalari vektor-funksiyalar uchun ham o'z kuchida qolishi kelib chiqadi.

Masalan: vektor-funksiyalar yig'indisining hosilasi qo'shiluvchi vektor-funksiyalar hosilalarining yig'indisiga teng.

Xususan, ikki vektor-funksiyalar yig'indisi uchun

$$(\vec{r}_1(t) + \vec{r}_2(t))' = \vec{r}_1'(t) + \vec{r}_2'(t) \quad (5)$$

ko'rinishdagi formula o'rinlidir.

Shunga o'xshash, O'zgarmas son ko'paytuvchisini hosila ishorasidan tashqariga

chiqarish mumkin:

$$\frac{d(a\vec{r}(t))}{dt} = a \frac{d\vec{r}}{dt} \quad (6)$$

Endi vektor-funksiyalarga xos amallar bilan bog'liq bo'lgan hosilani hisoblashning ba'zi qoidalarini keltiramiz. Bu qoidalarning isbotini o'quvchilarga mashq sifatida qoldiramiz.

1. Vektor-funksiyalarning skalyar ko'paytmasidan olingan hosila ushbu formula bilan ifodalanadi:

$$\frac{d(\vec{r}_1 \cdot \vec{r}_2)}{dt} = \frac{d\vec{r}_1}{dt} \cdot \vec{r}_2 + \vec{r}_1 \cdot \frac{d\vec{r}_2}{dt} \quad (7)$$

2. Agar $f(t)$ skalyar funksiya va $\vec{r}(t)$ vektor-funksiya bo'lsa, $f(t) \vec{r}(t)$ ko'paytmaning hosilasi ushbu formula bo'yicha hisoblanadi:

$$\frac{d(f(t)\vec{r}(t))}{dt} = \frac{df}{dt} \vec{r} + f \frac{d\vec{r}}{dt} \quad (8)$$

3. $\vec{r}_1(t)$ va $\vec{r}_2(t)$ vektor-funksiyalarning vektor ko'paytmasining hosilasi

formula bo'yicha topiladi.

$$\frac{d(\vec{r}_1 \times \vec{r}_2)}{dt} = a \frac{d\vec{r}_1}{dt} \times \vec{r}_2 + \vec{r}_1 \times \frac{d\vec{r}_2}{dt} \quad (9)$$

Vektor funksiya

Birorta G to'plam berilgan bo'lsin, Agar G to'plamning har bir nuqtasiga aniq bitta vector mos qo'yilgan bo'lsa, G to'plamda vector funksiya berilgan deyiladi. Bu moslikni

$p \Rightarrow \vec{r}(p)$ ko'rinishda yozing.

Ta'rif-1.

Berilgan $\vec{r}(p)$ vector funksiya va o'zgarmas \vec{a} vector uchun $p \rightarrow p_0$ da $|\vec{r}(p) - \vec{a}| \rightarrow 0$

Munosabat bajarilsa, $\vec{r}(p)$ vector $p \rightarrow p_0$ da \vec{a} limitga ega deyiladi va $\vec{r}(p) \rightarrow \vec{a}$ ko'rinishda yoziladi.

Bu yerda $|\vec{a}| = \sqrt{(\vec{a}, \vec{a})}$ bo'lib, (\vec{a}, \vec{a}) esa skalyar ko'paytmadir.

Agar formulada kiritilgan dekart kordinatalar sistemasida

$$\vec{r}(p) = \{x(p), y(p), z(p)\}, \vec{a} = \{a_1, a_2, a_3\} \text{ bo'lsa}$$

$p \rightarrow p_0$ da $\vec{r}(p) \rightarrow \vec{a}$ munosabat quyidagi uchta munosabatga ekvivalentdir.

$$\begin{aligned} x(p) &\rightarrow a_1 & y(p) &\rightarrow a_2 & z(p) &\rightarrow a_3 \\ p &\rightarrow p_0 & p &\rightarrow p_0 & p &\rightarrow p_0 \end{aligned}$$

Vector funksiya limiti uchun quyidagi teoremani o'rnlidir.

Ta'rif-6. Berilgan $\vec{r}(p), \vec{p}(p)$ vector funksiyalar va $\lim_{p \rightarrow p_0} \lambda(p) = \lambda_0$ tenglik bajarilsa, quyidagi munosabat o'rnlidir.

- 1) $r(p) \pm p(p) \xrightarrow{p \rightarrow p_0} \vec{a} \pm \vec{b}$
- 2) $\lambda(p)r(p) \xrightarrow{p \rightarrow p_0} \vec{a}$
- 3) $(r(p), p(p)) \xrightarrow{p \rightarrow p_0} (a, b)$
- 4) $[r(p), p(p)] \xrightarrow{p \rightarrow p_0} [a, b]$

1) $r(p) \pm p(p)$

$$\lim_{p \rightarrow p_0} (r(p) \pm p(p)) = a \pm b \Rightarrow \lim_{p \rightarrow p_0} r(p) = a, \lim_{p \rightarrow p_0} p(p) = b$$

isboti.

$$d(p) = r(p) \pm p(p), \vec{c} = \vec{a} + \vec{b}$$

$$\lim_{p \rightarrow p_0} |d(p) - c| = 0$$

$$|d(p) - c| = |(r(p) - a) \pm (p(p) - b)| \leq |r(p) - a| \pm |p(p) - b|$$

$$0 \leq 0$$

2) $\lim_{p \rightarrow p_0} \lambda(p)r(p) = \lambda_0 a$

$$|\lambda(p)r(p) - \lambda_0 a| \xrightarrow{p \rightarrow p_0} 0$$

$$|\lambda(p)r(p) + \lambda(p)a - \lambda(p)a| = |(\lambda(p)r(p) - a) + a(\lambda(p) - \lambda_0)| \leq$$

$$|(\lambda(p)r(p) - a)| + |a(\lambda(p) - \lambda_0)| = 0$$

3) $(r(p)p(p)) \xrightarrow{p \rightarrow p_0} (a, b)$

$$r(p) = \{x_1(p), y_1(p), z_1(p)\} \quad \begin{matrix} x_1(p) \Rightarrow a_1, \\ p \rightarrow p_0 \end{matrix} \quad \begin{matrix} y_1(p) \Rightarrow a_2, \\ p \rightarrow p_0 \end{matrix} \quad \begin{matrix} z_1(p) \Rightarrow a_3, \\ p \rightarrow p_0 \end{matrix}$$

$$p(p) = \{x_2(p), y_2(p), z_2(p)\} \quad \begin{matrix} x_2(p) \Rightarrow b_1, \\ p \rightarrow p_0 \end{matrix} \quad \begin{matrix} y_2(p) \Rightarrow b_2, \\ p \rightarrow p_0 \end{matrix} \quad \begin{matrix} z_2(p) \Rightarrow b_3, \\ p \rightarrow p_0 \end{matrix}$$

$$a = \{a_1, a_2, a_3\}$$

$$b = \{b_1, b_2, b_3\}$$

$$r(p)p(p) = \{x_1(p)x_2(p) + y_1(p)y_2(p) + z_1(p)z_2(p)\}$$

$$r(p)p(p) = (x_1(p), y_1(p), z_1(p)) \cdot (x_2(p), y_2(p), z_2(p)) = x_1(p)x_2(p) + y_1(p)y_2(p) + z_1(p)z_2(p)$$

$$= a_1b_1 + a_2b_2 + a_3b_3 = (a, b)$$

1) $(\lambda(p)r(p))' = \lambda'(p)r(p) + \lambda(p)r'(p)$

2) $(r(p) \pm p(p))' = r'(p) \pm p'(p)$

3) $(r(p), p(p))' = (r'(p), p(p)) + (r(p), p'(p))$

4) $[r(p), p(p)]' = [r'(p), p(p)] + [r(p), p'(p)]$

Isboti.

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \lambda(p)r(p) = \frac{\lambda(p+h)r(p+h) - \lambda(p)r(p)}{h} =$$

$$1) \frac{(\lambda(p+h) - \lambda(p))r(p+h) + \lambda(p)r(p+h) - \lambda(p)r(p)}{h} =$$

$$\lambda'(p)r(p) + r'(p)\lambda(p)$$

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} f(r(p) \pm p(p)) = \frac{f(r(p) \pm p(p+h)) - F(r(p) \pm p(p))}{h} =$$

$$2) \frac{(r(p+h) - r(p)) + r(p) \pm (p(p+h) - p(p)) + p(p) - (r(p) + p(p))}{h} =$$

$$r'(p) \pm p'(p)$$

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} (r(p), p(p)) = \frac{r(p+h), p(p+h) - r(p)p(p)}{h} =$$

$$3) \frac{(r(p+h) - r(p))p(p+h) + r(p)p(p+h) - r(p)p(p)}{h} =$$

$$= r'(p)p(p) + p'(p)r(p)$$

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} (r(p), p(p)) = \frac{r(p+h), p(p+h) - r(p)p(p)}{h} =$$

$$4) \frac{(r(p+h) - r(p))p(p+h) + r(p)p(p+h) - r(p)p(p)}{h} =$$

$$= r'(p)p(p) + p'(p)r(p)$$

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